

The Role and Importance of (Ego) and (Id) in the Psyche of Children in Adolescence

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the relationships that observed in adolescence, as well as relationships and the formation of ego and id in their psyche.

Keywords: Personality, adolescence, pubertal period, psyche, regression, id, and ego mechanism.

ACCESS

The person during the life of all the various instinktiv the importance of the process have always attracted the most attention from the period of the age of puberty. Sharpen sex for a long time has been the subject of psychological phenomena can appear, which means that the spiritual.study. We then ingtaiphrecible nonanalitik apparent conflict in the spiritual life and uncompromising in the works, above all, spiritual balance disturbances, this character will be changes in the definition and find many wonderful years. An extreme egoist teenagers themselves the center of the universe is a single object of interest to know that, but they never are not capable of selfless devotion, and in the next life. Most of them passionate love the form of the relationship, just as suddenly they will start uzar. On the one hand, they themselves were removed with enthusiasm to the life of society, on the other hand, solitude they want very ... That is, this is simply physiological transformations of spiritual accompaniment. The other theory rejects the idea of any such link between the physical and the spiritual. According to him, the spiritual sphere that happened in the revolution of the person to achieve is a sign of mental can simply sharpen, can sharpen the physical changes physical signs at the same time. As noted, at the same time a group of mental and physical processes appear to be evidence that the cause of the other is not. Thus, the second theory is completely independent from the process, it was noted that development and glandular psixik instinktiv.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY.

Psychological features are exactly the person the child the age of puberty, adolescence and the changes happen in a certain amount of davirda or not at a high price to give me his psychic of his peers and family in the circle of scientific researchers from research on the quality of a certain amount agresivlik qo'p be observed, and in particular this works during a survey whose psychoanalytic study of this article, 2:189-228. London: Hogarth Press. JONES, E. (1922), some problem of Adolescence. On paper Psy-Analysis. London: Baillifre, Tindall & Cox, 5th ed., 1948, pp. 389-

406. , Narsisizm Pathological. In: psychology and Ego are psixoz. London: Xogart press, 1952, 323-364 page. , Freyd, ANNA (1926-27), technical access to the child in an institution , Analysis. The analysis in the introductory part psixoanaliz children on excursion to reports. London: Xogart Press, 1974, HOWEVER, M. (1932) The Psychoanalysis of children The ego and the MECHANISMS of defence by anna freud revised edition book this book was originally published in germany in 1936 the london KARNAC. The English translation was published in 1937 and reprinted in 1942 by Cecil Baines , 1947, 1954, I96 and 0, with a new Foreword in 1966. The present revised edition, based on the 7 193 translation, was first published in the united states in 1966, and by 1968 the Hogarth Press in this country Ltd. reprinted 1972 , 1976, 1979, 1986. Reprinted by the missionary with the H . Karnac (Book) Ltd, 1993. 118 finchley road, london NW 3 5H T . Analysis and synthesis of scientific research carried out by scientists know this researcher quotes, complex approach has to rely on methods such as content analysis and the role of the id, the ego and the world in the way of teenage life lit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carried out by researchers has identified the same thing during the period of adolescence at the age of puberty, such as their psixik and mental blocks that monitor is one of the stages of development of human life. Infantile sexual recapitulation this period, the first; in the next period of life, the latter climacterica happens. Sex and the resuscitation of each period of the previous period is the update. Also, of course, specific to each contribute to the sexual life of one man. Physical sex can sharpen at the age of puberty to achieve for some reason, this period occupies the first position in the pregenital and genital trends from the members of the sex instinct is superior components. Climacterica, physical, sexual function decreased when the genital and pregenital impulses impulses flaming again the last time will appear by itself.

Psychanalysis works until now was mostly concerned with the similarities between the life of man in this period of turbulent sexual three. A quantitative relationship between the ego and instinct they close to each other in power is like most. In each case, early infantile period, and at the age of puberty klimakterikada—id weaker than stronger than he comes face to ego. So, we enfeebled id ego and make them strong when I can say that. In addition, in this period three ego-id from a strong resemblance than one two factors in the relationship quality.

The relationship between the ego and the id of this difference from the first two factors, namely the transformative of the human ego will come out great. Id ego is not compatible with the change of the variation. For example, let's ego and ego get in early childhood in the age of puberty. In the second period and a compass, content, knowledge and options, are subject to vary with the relationship of the applicant and anxiety. Consequently, it uses one of the different protection mechanisms in different periods of conflict with instinct. These differences in early infancy and the age of puberty to learn more, instinktiv similar between the coverage as with the study of this period of his life, the ego, we can expect the formation of scattered light that would. Check processes instinktiv, as I am also studying the development strengthening the ego later on just as before I can understand.

Please explain before we responsible at puberty disorders, ego W, ego need to understand the nature of the situation in the period of early infancy. The conflict between the ego and the id of the specific circumstances in small children has to. Oral, anal and falls to the phase of typical requirements that come out extraordinary and very satisfied from the desire instinktiv live the fantasy and the effects associated with edip kastratsiya very complex and complicated; only the ego that is in the process of faced them. formation and therefore still weak and underdeveloped. Despite this, jilov minor children without the pressure and anxiety instinktiv instinct is not under normal conditions it is not aware of. In the outside world, against life in the effects of influencing educational instinktiv him that his weak ego has a powerful ally. The situation does not arise, then the power should be measured against instinktiv powerful impulses of his ego so strong, if it gets you, it should be submitted on the basis of inevitable.

Your instinct to be aware of in relation to their own wishes to the children or to assume that his strength is weak or does not leave almost time for you. Her ego is simply the relationship of the child's other people's promises and threats, that is, with the expectation of punishment and the hope of love is set. Under external effects such small children, within a few years, instinctive have great potential for the management of their own life, but you may not need to determine how qanchasi of these achievements tied to their ego by foreign powers direct pressure. The ego self of the child in this situation of conflict with external side-effects to put the child "good."Instinktiv limit imposed by this part gets id and education meet him to fight against if it is" naughty."Learn more infantile ego and the id of the external world dedicated to these fluctuations between pedagogical science. It looking for closer union between the ego and drafting tools of education and the master of the general struggle for the power of their instinct to be more successful. However, there is little conflict in children endopsixik if you can't get this education. Soon the children of the world outside the spiritual mode, set the lens represented in the form of anxiety. Such concern itself appear to be of higher institutions in ego—superego development of conscience or the evidence of it is not in his but this is a pioneer. Lens worry-this can be delivered to the children by the foreign agent to meet the suffering that the punishment always does the expected punishment, whether or not the behavior of managing ego "forepain" 's a type. On the one hand, this anxiety in proportion to those who are in contact with the child behavior dangerous or volatile is sharp.

On the other hand, it will be strengthened with the process of instinctive turned against itself, often combined with the anxiety that arises from fantasy and does not record the changes of the lens, therefore its touch with reality will increasingly go relax. Concerns in the minds of little children with infantile neurosis clear and sharp instinktiv emergency requirements of the lens in an attempt to solve this conflict cause the symptoms of conflict. This internal struggle is the basis of the study and description of a debate among scientists: some of them pedagogical region are considered within the framework of their theory of neurosis that is at the same time I am sure. Another specific feature of ego in the mode of the minor child if there is not, it will never be repeated in the next life. Then all the fighters are also already available, both in defense situation: is it hard to face it more or less need to come with ego instinct. However, the little children in the conflict itself completion of construction, the ego, and the ego that must be engaged in the task of mastering life is the instinct for only the side of the lens in this early period requirements and joint instinktiv id under the pressure of anxiety is

born. of foreign origin. Ego measure "made you say," 1 ie. better adapted to hold the balance between two forces: without the pressure of desire and instinct.

In the meantime, it is more powerful than the outside world; and the world less helpless and obedient as before it is not that powerful. His attitude will change when going from the whole to the status edip gradually increased foreign objects. Parents love to take the place of full stops dependence and begin object identification. More and more parents and teachers the child up by his principles—their wishes, requirements, and of the ideali—there are introjected. Now the anxiety of her inner life in the form of the lens himself in the outside world just doesn't feel. It has established permanent institutions in which educational methods for children ultramodern their ego "to measure", can be described as an attempt to make the external world, the superego, call our requirements and made those around her. With this development happens at the same time to change the baby's anxiety.

Fear the old and new is really big from the outside world slowly gives a place to the fear of the representatives of power-anxiety, feeling of guilt and anxiety of conscience. This means that the period of delay instinktiv have a new ally in the fight for mastering the processes of the ego. Conscience of anxiety, the anxiety is the cause of the sucker of the lens in the same period as the delay in the period from instinct to protect requires. As before, taken during the period of the delay of the ego self and the instinct of how superegoing control over how strong the effect depends on whether it is difficult to determine. However, the long latency period is provided with the respiratory area will not continue. Two antagonists, the ego and the id the struggle between the radical agreement before the end of the terms of this temporary strengthened with fighters modified with one of sulh is almost over. Physical sex can sharpen your libido to defining achievement of physiological processes in the form of the flow processes held to instinktiv comes with the stimulation of the spiritual sphere.

The power of the relationship between ego and id is not established, painful mental achieved the right balance is broken, as a result, the internal conflict between the two institutions from the new fire. At first, there are little things on the side to give the report id. Delay and the range to reach puberty-prepubertal period, which is called the period—this is simply to prepare physical sexual sharpen. The change did not happen instinktiv now no quality of life, but increased the amount of energy instinktiv. He already knows his mind. Infantile ego rebels against union with the outside world was suddenly able to lift and get satisfaction instinctive id to make, however you do it of youthful ego, superego faced with he is involved in. On the one hand a strong connection with his id and superego on the other hand—the thing which we call character—makes it resistant to the ego. This one may desire to know: developed during the delay period, the character will retain their previous relationship of power between the forces of the id and instinktiv and recovery actual self-defense to respond to twice as act requirements. Conscience and the ego to maintain their presence in this struggle with anxiety and concern of the lens and encouraging all who applied during the delay period equal to the period sucker gratuitous use of conservation methods. Repressiya this download, deny, and reverses of instinct and turn them against himself; this produces the symptoms of anxiety, phobias and obsessive thinking and behavior through the hysteria and connects.

If we fight for supremacy between the ego and the id we consider this with a meticulous, almost all of the phenomena we prepubertal period coming on means of irritating to the various stages

of the conflict. Active Ghost increased pregenital (i.e. corrupt) sexual content, partial success means the id of offensive or criminal actions, in the form of a variety of anxiety appears to be, and the development of more powerful features and symptoms astsetik nevrotik inhibisyonlarning aksentuatsiyasi means protection, i.e. the id of the sleeve success means. the success of the ego. The body can reach sexual sharpen with the beginning of the age of puberty, once again changes, this time a quality character. Instinktiv kateksisning the general escalation so far, I was able to farqlanmagan nature; now a change happens (for men, at any rate), becomes the full power of genital impulses. This libidinal impulses in the pregenital and genital feelings kateksisning be pulled out from the spiritual sphere, objects concentrated on the idea of goals and means.

Prepubertal period in his life and who are wondering youthful character of pregenital instinct responsible for the education of those who are now concerned with ourselves, as turbulent and corrupt behavior of the whole of that had disappeared like tajovuzkorlik are noted with relief. This can be achieved sexual erkaklik even break the boundaries of social convention, the judgment is met with much more comfortable and neglect. However, this physiological treatment pregenitality spontaneous, the natural result of the development that happens at the age of puberty, mainly deceitful. Very large at the age of puberty, which is when the pressure falls to a normal level of instinct in adult life, concerns and disputes, perhaps, will interfere with the affairs of his men, and again appear unchanged. Despite this, in the period that falls in the period of childhood and prepubertal boys who tend to be in the interests dominate, oral and anal ko'rgazmachilikka when at the age of puberty may not be kompensatsion effects. The internal defense and conflict continues in this large values are ignored.

Identifikator relationship during adolescence in terms of the quality of the ego in the first place, but is determined from the quantitative aspect. That's the point, it is not the satisfaction or frustration of desire it or not this instinktiv, but in the structure and the nature of spiritual childhood delay and in general in general. There are two extreme situations that may be the end of the conflict. Now the ego or the id of the strong growth can be overcome in this case does not remain no trace of the previous character of the person to enter adult life satisfaction is determined by the revolt of instinct and unlimited. Or the ego can be overcome, in this case the character of the person will fix all of the good and for the period of the delay of the self. When this happens, the impulses of the id of the child's instinktiv teenager is limited in the narrow limits marked for life. But this simple observation is inconsistent with the explanation in the analyst in the process of puberty the young person.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Cases observed in adolescence period of adolescence as that observed in the physiological reasons are stronger instinct of when you will have more compassion for the person or on the other hand, this phenomenon is more prominent with the decrease of the power of spiritual instinct. id ego and superego the part of the more than more big plays. Nevrotik we know from the study cases and symptoms before menstruation, when the demands become more pressing of instinct, ego defense will be forced to increase the activity two times. On the other hand, claims less instinktiv when clicked, the anxiety of the lens decreases and with it the risk associated with them, the conscience and

the ego by instinct to anxiety will worry. The latter is completely under water by id, with the exception of the remaining cases, we find the opposite of the relationship we offer.

Instinctive enhances resistance to pressure of any additional requirements that instinct of ego and symptoms, enhances the inhibition etc., resistance to this based on instinct you less urgent, more will be willing to give permission to the soft and ego satisfaction. This means that the age of puberty in the absolute power of the instinct (in any case, it can not be independently measured or estimated) of the age of puberty does not issue the final forecasts. Relative the factors that determine it: first of all, with the power of id impulses of age of puberty conditioned physiological process; and secondly, the character formed during the period of delay or tolerance of the ego which is related to instinct does not tolerate; third-and this is the quality of the quantitative factor solve this conflict-protection mechanism of the ego with the order of the nature and effectiveness, this is the constitution of a certain person, that is, his or obsessive neurosis developed a predisposition to hysteria, so that in this period will vary with line and it also means you need to be in a relationship exactly in relation to children in them because in this period inqroz period is observ

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